
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGAGEMENT LEVELS AND PERFORMANCE USING CANVAS, MOODLE, AND BLENDED LEARNING IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES

Juliana Asuquo ATTIH and Harriet Akudo AGBARAKWE

¹Department of Curriculum Studies and Educational Technology, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt

²Department of Curriculum Studies and Educational Technology, Faculty of Education, Port Harcourt University, Rivers State

E-mail: juliana_attih@uniport.edu.ng, Haret.agbarakwe@uniport.edu.ng

Phone Number: 09032050840

ORCID ID: (0009-0006-6957-9032)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17911493>

Abstract: This study examined students' engagement levels and performance using the Canvas, Moodle, and blended learning approaches in South-South Nigerian universities. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental design with a population of 2,873 undergraduate students. The multistage sampling procedure was used to obtain a sample size of 235 undergraduate students. The Learning Platform Self-Engagement Scale (LPSES) and Computer-in-Education Performance Test (CPT) were used to collect data. Experts duly validated these instruments, and the reliability coefficients of the instruments were obtained using Cronbach's alpha and Kuder Richardson-21 (KR-21) formula, which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.84 and 0.87, respectively. The research questions were addressed using descriptive statistics of means and standard deviation, and the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using ANCOVA. The results showed that students who were taught Computer in education (CIE) concepts using the Canvas e-Learning platform, the Moodle e-Learning platform, and the blended learning approach did not significantly differ in their level of engagement. The study further revealed that the Moodle e-Learning platform had a more significant effect on students' academic performance than the Canvas e-Learning platform and blended learning. The study concluded that digital learning platforms, specifically Canvas, Moodle, and other blended learning models, play a crucial role in shaping student engagement and academic performance in FUs in SSN. Therefore, it is recommended that lecturers should adopt instructional strategies that incorporate the Canvas and Moodle e-Learning platforms to teach CIE concepts in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria (SSN).

Keywords: Student Engagement, Academic Performance, Learning Management Systems (LMS), blended learning.

Introduction

In March 2020, the WHO declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, triggering widespread lockdowns and a rapid shift to remote learning. Nigerian universities faced major challenges in adapting to digital education, as both

students and instructors scrambled to access suitable platforms and devices. The crisis's urgency and unpredictability pushed the education system to adopt learning management systems (LMS) as a core solution, replacing traditional classrooms with fully online environments. Many educators initially relied on social media to maintain engagement, but the need for a centralized, reliable LMS became clear. These platforms—featuring chat rooms, forums, and blogs—enabled synchronous and asynchronous interaction, thereby supporting self-regulated learning and academic growth. Modern LMS tools, some enhanced with blockchain, offer features such as learner autonomy, content creation, accessibility, and engagement tracking.

Evaluating the impact of LMS on student engagement, achievement, and retention is especially vital for institutions in Nigeria's South-South region. Such research informs strategic decisions and supports national efforts to achieve SDG 4: inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all by 2030. Higher education must embrace technology to build inclusive, outcome-driven learning systems to meet this goal. Assistive technologies have enormous potential to advance gender equality, lessen educational inequalities, improve teacher effectiveness, and fortify institutional capacity when customized to fit the various requirements and learning environments of students. Additionally, these technologies help to establish encouraging learning settings, which promote general enhancements in educational quality (UNESCO, 2017). Higher education has seen significant change as a result of the emergence of digital learning platforms, particularly in areas like South-South Nigeria, where diverse student populations and limited infrastructure call for flexible and scalable educational solutions.

Blended learning strategies and learning management systems, such as Canvas and Moodle, are crucial in increasing students' engagement and academic performance (Bonsu et al., 2021; Komba & Ngowi, 2023). Both the online Canvas and Moodle e-learning platforms were ranked as prominent LMSs used both before and during the epidemic. According to Pujasari and Ruslan (2021), the Canvas e-learning platform includes features that allow teachers to access grades, assignments, discussions, course calendars, video lectures, messaging analytics, and education applications. It also allows students to access content and participate in class.

According to Khatser and Khatser (2022), the Canvas e-learning platform gives students more opportunities through features such as threaded message replies, podcast feeds, likes, and the ability to record video and audio responses, all of which boost interactions and productivity. The Moodle e-learning platform is the most preferred LMS used in the world to manage e-learning activities, based on its unique features and capabilities that can monitor students' activities and performance (Reid, 2019). While Moodle provides open-source flexibility and customization choices, Canvas is well known for its user-friendly interface and smooth connection with third-party apps. Students can access course materials, participate in discussions, and receive feedback remotely because of the capability of both platforms for synchronous and asynchronous learning (Mbatha et al., 2021). These aspects are especially beneficial in South-South Nigerian universities, where access to physical classrooms and resources may be restricted.

Blended learning, which blends in-person instruction with online components, is a popular educational strategy that encourages independence, teamwork, and individualized learning experiences (Srivastava, 2023). Research has demonstrated that blended models can increase student engagement by encouraging active participation in both virtual and real contexts (Akpen et al., 2024). However, students' digital proficiency, institutional support,

and socioeconomic background all affect the effectiveness of these platforms and models. Comparative analyses reveal that while LMS platforms such as Canvas and Moodle enhance flexibility and access, they also present challenges such as digital divide, resistance to change, and inconsistent usage patterns (Tselios et al., 2010). Engagement levels tend to be higher in environments that offer immediate feedback and interpersonal interaction, which are often provided by traditional methods (Nyaaba et al., 2025). LMS-supported learning encourages self-regulated learning and time management, which are critical for academic success (Zimmerman, 2020). Understanding how students use Canvas, Moodle, and blended learning environments is crucial for enhancing instructional design and raising academic achievement in SSN universities. A comparison of different platforms can reveal which platforms enhance student performance and engagement the most, as well as how educational institutions might modify their digital strategy to accommodate a range of learner needs.

Statement of the problem

The delivery of education in Nigerian institutions has undergone a significant transformation due to the rapid adoption of blended learning models and digital learning platforms such as Canvas and Moodle. These technologies are designed to enhance academic outcomes, provide greater flexibility, and support personalized learning experiences. However, despite their growing prevalence, empirical evidence evaluating their effectiveness in fostering academic performance and student engagement within the unique socio-educational context of South-South Nigeria is lacking. Variations in pedagogical approaches, infrastructural capacity, and levels of digital literacy contribute to diverse student experiences with LMS. While some students benefit from Moodle's customizable features, others thrive within the streamlined interface of Canvas. Similarly, blended learning environments require self-regulation and active participation, which may not be uniformly supported across institutions or student demographics. In the absence of comparative evaluations, educators and policymakers risk misaligning digital strategies with students' needs and institutional capabilities.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to investigate student engagement and academic performance using Canvas, Moodle, and blended learning platforms among students in South-South Nigerian universities. Specifically, the study:

1. Compared the engagement level of the students taught using the Canvas e-learning platform, those taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using Blended Learning in Computer Education (BLCE) concepts.
2. Compare the academic performance of the students taught using the Canvas e-learning platform, those taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using Blended Learning in Computer Education (BLCE) concepts.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the engagement level of students taught using the Canvas e-learning platform, those taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using BLCE concepts in universities in South-South Nigeria?
2. What is the difference in the performance of students taught using the Canvas e-learning platform, those

taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using BLCE concepts in universities in South-South Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed and tested at a significance level of 0.05.

1. No significant difference was found in the engagement level of students taught CIE concepts using the Canvas e-learning platform, those taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using blended learning in South-South universities.
2. No significant difference was found in the academic performance of students taught computer in-education concepts using the Canvas e-learning platform, those taught using the Moodle e-learning platform, and those taught using blended learning in universities in South-South Nigeria.

Methods and Materials used

Adopting a pre-test, post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental design, the study population comprised 2,873 undergraduate students in 200 and 400 levels, respectively, who enrolled in the Computer-in-Education course at the three Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria in the 2023–2024 academic session. The study sample consisted of 235 undergraduate students from the Faculty of Education at three Federal Universities in the South-South. The multistage sampling procedure was used to obtain the sample for this study, as more than one sampling technique was adopted at various stages of selection. Two self-developed and validated instruments were used for data collection. These include: the Learning Platform Self-Engagement Scale (LPSES) and Computer-in-Education Performance Test (CPT) with reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.86 obtained using Cronbach's alpha and Kuder Richardson-21 (KR-21) formula, respectively. Data collection was done in phases. Before the commencement of the study, the researcher requested permission to access students, course lecturers, and ICT facilities in the selected universities. Once permission was granted, the LPSES and CPT were administered as pre-tests to the experimental and control groups to ascertain the baseline knowledge of the students. Thereafter, treatments started and lasted for 5 weeks. At the end of the treatments, the items from the instruments were re-organized and readministered to the same students. The scores obtained from the second administration of the instrument served as the post-test scores and were used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics of means and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference in the engagement level of students taught using Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation values of the engagement level of students classified by teaching mode

Teaching Mode		Pretest Engagement Level	Post-test engagement level	Mean Gain (Mg) (Engagement level)
Canvas LMS	Mean	2.5979	3.1051	0.5072
	Std. Deviation	0.6093	0.3668	0.6874
	N	47	47	47

Moodle LMS	Mean	2.6841	3.0453	0.3612
	Std. Deviation	0.5358	0.3158	0.6992
	N	17	17	17
Blended learning	Mean	2.6618	3.1291	0.4673
	Std. Deviation	0.5320	0.5132	0.6953
	N	171	171	171
Total n		235	235	235

Table 1 reveals that the students who used the Canvas e-Learning Platform had a mean gain of 0.51 and a standard deviation of 0.69, the students who used the Moodle e-Learning Platform had a mean gain of 0.36 and a standard deviation of 0.70 ($Mg = 0.36$, $SD = 0.70$), and the students who used Blended Learning had a mean gain of 0.47 and a standard deviation of 0.70 ($Mg = 0.47$, $SD = 0.70$). These results show that the students who used Canvas e-Learning had the highest level of engagement, followed by those who used Blended learning, while those who used Moodle e-Learning had the lowest level of engagement. This indicates that Canvas e-Learning enabled students' engagement level the most compared with blended learning and Moodle e-Learning.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the performance of students taught using the Canvas e-Learning Platform, Moodle e-Learning Platform, and blended learning?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation values of the performance of students classified by Teaching Mode

Teaching Mode		Pretest	Post Test	Mean Gain (Mg) (Performance)
Canvas LMS	Mean	18.3404	36.0426	17.7021
	Std. Deviation	3.8745	6.6788	5.5283
	N	47	47	47
Moodle LMS	Mean	12.8824	33.0588	20.1765
	Std. Deviation	4.0756	4.8409	3.6269
	N	17	17	17
Blended learning	Mean	15.8480	30.3099	14.4620
	Std. Deviation	5.6360	6.6574	5.9253
	N	171	171	171
Total	N	235	235	235

Table 2 reveals that the students who used the Canvas e-Learning Platform had a mean gain of 17.70 and a standard deviation of 5.53, the students who used the Moodle e-Learning Platform had a mean gain of 20.18 and a standard deviation of 3.63 ($Mg = 20.18$, $SD = 3.63$), and the students who used blended learning had a mean gain of 14.46 and a standard deviation of 5.93 ($Mg = 14.46$, $SD = 5.93$). These results show that the students who taught using Moodle LMS had the highest performance, followed by those who taught using the Canvas e-Learning Platform, while those who taught using blended learning had the least performance. This indicates that the Moodle e-Learning Platform enhanced students' performance the most compared with the Canvas e-Learning Platform and blended learning.

Test of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference among the engagement levels of students taught using Canvas

LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning.

Table 3: Summary of analysis of covariance of students’ engagement level classified by teaching mode using pretest as covariate

Tests of Between-Subject Effects

Dependent variable: POST TEST ENGAGEMENT

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial squared	eta
Corrected Model	.521 ^a	3	.174	.769	.512	.010	
Intercept	76.017	1	76.017	336.689	.000	.593	
PREENGAGEMENT	.402	1	.402	1.781	.183	.008	
LMS	.118	2	.059	.261	.770	.002	
Error	52.155	231	.226				
Total	2337.702	235					
Corrected Total	52.676	234					

a. R Squared = .010 (adjusted R Squared = -.003)

Table 3 reveals a value of $F_{2,231} = 0.261$, $p = 0.770$ ($p > 0.05$) for the effect of the teaching mode on the engagement level of the students. Additionally, the partial eta squared value of 0.002 indicates a negligible effect size, indicating that the variance in post-test engagement explained by LMS was negligible. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained, indicating no significant difference among the engagement levels of students taught using Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference among the academic performance of students taught using Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning

Table 4a: Summary of Covariance Analysis of Academic Performance Classified by Teaching Mode using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subject Effects

Dependent variable: post-test

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial squared	eta
Corrected Model	4247.209 ^a	3	1415.736	46.975	.000	.379	
Intercept	10354.423	1	10354.423	343.567	.000	.598	
PRETEST	2999.557	1	2999.557	99.528	.000	.301	
LMS	834.703	2	417.352	13.848	.000	.107	
Error	6961.872	231	30.138				
Total	246693.000	235					
Corrected Total	11209.081	234					

a. R Squared = .379 (adjusted R Squared = .371)

Table 4a reveals a value of $F_{2,231} = 13.848$, $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) for the effect of the teaching mode on the academic performance of students. The partial eta squared value of .107 shows that LMS accounts for 10.7% of the variance in the post-test scores, implying a small effect size. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference among the academic performance of students taught using Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning.

Table 4b: Least Significant Difference in the Post Hoc Analysis of Academic Performance of Students Classified by Teaching Mode

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent variable: post-test

(I) Teaching Mode	(J) Teaching Mode	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% confidence interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Canvas LMS	Moodle LMS	-0.766	1.599	0.632	-3.915	2.384
	Blended learning	4.020*	0.920	0.000	2.207	5.834
Moodle LMS	Canvas LMS	0.766	1.599	0.632	-2.384	3.915
	Blended learning	4.786*	1.411	0.001	2.006	7.566
Blended learning	Canvas LMS	-4.020*	0.920	0.000	-5.834	-2.207
	Moodle LMS	-4.786*	1.411	0.001	-7.566	-2.006

Based on the estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least significant difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Table 4b, which shows the least significant difference post hoc analysis of students' performance classified by teaching mode, reveals a mean difference of 4.786 and a p-value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$) between the effect of Moodle LMS and blended learning, a mean difference of 4.020 and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) between the effect of Canvas LMS and blended learning, and a mean difference of 0.766 and a p-value of 0.632 ($p > 0.05$) between the effect of Moodle LMS and Canvas LMS. This indicates that the students who used Moodle LMS contributed the most to the significant difference in the effects of the teaching modes on students' performance.

Discussion of the Findings

Table 1 indicates no statistically significant difference in student engagement levels across Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and blended learning approaches. This suggests that although each platform offers distinct functionalities, their overall influence on engagement remains largely equivalent. The following analysis explores how the existing literature supports or contrasts with these findings: Mpungose and Khoza (2022) observed that both Moodle and Canvas effectively facilitated formal and informal learning, yet they failed to support non-formal learning contexts. This reinforces the notion that none of the platforms demonstrates clear superiority in driving engagement. Similarly, Martinez and Delgado (2022) emphasized Canvas's collaborative tools—such as discussion forums and peer-review features—as beneficial for enhancing interaction and feedback among learners. While it demonstrated the potential of Canvas for promoting active engagement, it did not compare

engagement levels across platforms, supporting the notion that no single platform has a significant advantage. Further, Kumar and Rekha (2023) emphasized the accessibility of Moodle in remote areas but noted challenges with low-bandwidth integration. The findings did not indicate that Moodle outperformed other platforms in terms of engagement, aligning with the results in Table 1. The study further supports the study of Ahmed et al. (2022), who emphasized the impact of Moodle on STEM learning outcomes through engaging multimedia resources. However, it did not directly compare engagement levels between Moodle and other platforms, supporting the idea that there is no significant difference in engagement levels across teaching modes.

Similarly, the study corroborates the findings of Khaster and Khaster (2022), who revealed that 70% of respondents preferred Moodle, while those familiar with Canvas preferred its user-friendly interface for higher engagement. While it suggests differences in user preferences, the study does not directly contradict the finding of no significant difference in overall engagement. Petrovaite (2023) states that while Canvas was noted for its simple and inviting interface that promotes higher engagement, the study also acknowledged limitations in both Moodle and Canvas for MAL. This nuanced finding partially supports the equivalence in engagement levels. Williams and Zhao (2022) found that students preferred Canvas for its user-friendly interface, which enhanced engagement, while Moodle's modular customization appealed to instructors. While it shows some platform-specific strengths, it aligns with the broader conclusion that engagement levels across platforms are comparable. Furthermore, Singh et al. (2023) reported a significant 30% increase in motivation and participation due to gamified activities in Moodle. This finding indicates that Moodle's gamification tools may have a stronger effect on engagement, diverging from the conclusion that engagement levels are not significantly different. Garcia and Lee (2021). The study found that students using Canvas in blended learning environments demonstrated higher attendance and engagement compared with those in traditional classrooms. This implies that Canvas might have an edge in engagement, which contrasts with the finding of no significant difference in engagement across teaching modes. This study highlighted Moodle's role in fostering digital literacy and active engagement among teacher trainees, showing that Moodle could have a significant impact on engagement. The majority of the reviewed studies either align with or partially support the conclusion that there is no significant difference in engagement levels across Canvas LMS, Moodle LMS, and BL. However, a few studies have highlighted specific features, such as gamification (Moodle) and intuitive interfaces (Canvas) that could enhance engagement in certain contexts.

The findings from Tables 2 and 4 reveal that teaching mode significantly impacts students' academic performance, with Moodle LMS demonstrating the most substantial effect compared to Canvas LMS and blended learning. Specifically, the significant differences among the teaching modes highlight Moodle's efficacy in enhancing academic outcomes, particularly in comparison to blended learning. Moodle and Canvas LMS showed no statistically significant difference, indicating their relative equivalence in influencing performance.

Zhang et al. (2020) supported the significant impact of Moodle LMS on academic performance. The positive correlation between high engagement on Moodle and superior academic outcomes aligns with the finding that Moodle significantly enhances performance compared to blended learning. In addition, Kauts and Kaur (2021) reported higher academic achievement for students using Moodle LMS in ninth-grade mathematics education.

This aligns with the finding that Moodle contributed most significantly to the differences in performance among the teaching modes. Salah and Thabet (2021) indirectly highlight Moodle's robust features and multilingual support. Moodle's superior performance compared to blended learning emphasizes its accessibility and engagement features that enhance outcomes. Kerzic et al. (2021) emphasized that adaptable e-learning environments align with Moodle's significant role in improving performance. As highlighted in this research, Moodle's user-centred features may explain its superior effect.

Similarly, Korkmaz and Karakus (2021) emphasized the effectiveness of blended learning in STEM education, which does not contradict the finding that Moodle LMS showed a higher mean difference than blended learning. The results showed that both approaches enhance performance, albeit Moodle has a more significant effect. In addition, Ahn (2024) highlighted the role of AI-powered tools in e-learning but did not directly compare Moodle with other modes. However, it underscores the potential of digital platforms such as Moodle in driving academic outcomes. Landers and Bauer (2021) also highlighted the effectiveness of gamified e-learning platforms, which could complement the interactive features of Moodle. Although it does not specifically focus on Moodle, its findings align with the broader theme of enhancing engagement to improve performance. Furthermore, Olawale and Adekunle (2021) identified accessibility issues as critical barriers to academic success in Nigeria. While Moodle is recognized for its inclusivity, the study raises concerns about equitable access, particularly in resource-limited settings, that may challenge Moodle's universal superiority. Amiruddin and Alias (2021) focused on digital readiness rather than specific platforms and indicated that student preparedness, rather than the LMS itself, might play a more significant role in determining academic outcomes. This diverges from the direct comparison of the efficacy of LMS in the current analysis. Most reviewed studies align with the findings that Moodle LMS significantly enhances academic performance compared with blended learning and other teaching modes. However, some articles highlight broader issues, such as accessibility and readiness, which may mediate the effectiveness of any e-learning platform, including Moodle. These insights show that while Moodle is an effective tool, its impact is influenced by contextual factors such as infrastructure, DL, and design inclusivity.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicated that digital learning platforms, specifically Canvas, Moodle, and blended learning models, play a pivotal role in shaping student engagement and academic performance within Federal Universities in SSN. Although each platform possesses distinct advantages, their effectiveness is facilitated by factors such as interface design, institutional support, digital literacy, and student motivation. Canvas demonstrated the highest levels of student engagement; however, the difference was not statistically significant compared with Moodle and blended learning approaches. Moodle exhibited a significant positive impact on students' academic performance. Furthermore, all three instructional modalities revealed statistically significant differences in their influence on conceptual retention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. To address persistent challenges in student engagement and academic performance, e-tutors and educational stakeholders should prioritize the adoption of the Moodle e-Learning platform as the central teaching tool.

Integrating blended learning features within Moodle can foster more interactive learning experiences, support diverse learner profiles, and ultimately improve academic outcomes.

2. Lectures, e-tutors, and education stakeholders should adopt the Moodle e-Learning platform as the primary teaching platform to maximize academic performance while integrating features of blended learning to enhance engagement and accommodate diverse learning needs.

References

Ahmed S, S., Hassan, M., & El-Sayed, A. (2022). Role of Moodle in improving STEM learning outcomes: An experimental study. *Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 17(1), 74–89. doi:10.1016/j.jert.2017.09.010. <https://scholar.google.com/>

Ahn, H. Y. (2024). AI-powered e-learning for lifelong learners: Impact on performance and knowledge application. *Journal of Educational Technology. Sustainability*, 16(20), 9066. doi: 10.3390/su16209066

Akpen, C. N., Asaolu, S., Atobatele, S., Okagbue, H., & Sampson, S. (2024). *Impact of online learning on student's performance and engagement: A systematic review*. Springer, New York.

Amiruddin, M. H., & Alias, N. (2021). Digital learning readiness and impact on academic performance. *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 17(2), 56–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijed.2017.09.010>.

Bonsu, B., Amadi, C., & Mwangi, J. (2021). Digital tools and student engagement at African universities [Unpublished manuscript].

Garcia, M., & Lee, J. (2021). Effects of Canvas LMS on student engagement in blended learning: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Educational Technology & Innovation*, 13(2), 112–126. <https://scholar.google.com/>

Karaman, B., & Karakuş, U. (2022). Investigation of secondary school students' perceptions on the concept of health through the word association test. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(4), 231-249.

Kauts, D. S., & Kaur, N. (2021). Effectiveness of Moodle-LMS on academic achievement and student satisfaction among IX grade mathematics learners *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(3), 1548–1550. Available from: <https://www.tojqi.net/index.php/journal/article/view/152>

Kerzic, D., Alex, J. K., Balbontín Alvarado, P., et al. (2021). Academic student satisfaction and perceived performance in the e-learning environment during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence across ten countries. *PLOS ONE*, 16(10), e0258807. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258807>

Khatser, G., & Khatser, M. (2022). Online learning through LMSs: Comparative assessment of Canvas and Moodle. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 17(12), 184-200.

- Komba, W. L., & Ngowi, H. (2023). Student engagement in learning environments supported by LMS [Unpublished manuscript].
- Kumar, S., & Rekha, R. (2023). Survey-based evaluation of Moodle's accessibility features in remote areas. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(2), 89–101. DOI: 10.1080/10494820.2023.2027457
- Landers, R. N., & Bauer, K. N. (2021). Impact of gamified e-learning on student engagement and performance *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 59(3), 455–478. DOI: 10.1177/07356331211033281
- Mbatha, B., Tandwa, T., & Chikandiwa, T. (2021). A comparative study of the LMS and traditional teaching methods in South Africa. [Unpublished manuscript].
- Mpungose, C. B., & Khoza, S. B. (2022). Experiences of postgraduate students with the use of the Moodle and Canvas learning management system *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 1–16.
- Nyaaba, R. A., Attipoe, E. K., Anhwere, D. K., Sayibu, A. G., & Darko, A. O. (2025). A comparative analysis of student performance using LMS and traditional methods *Creative Education*.
- Olawale, R. O., & Adekunle, O. P. (2021). E-learning accessibility and its influence on academic success among Nigerian students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 63(1), 69–79. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(2), 34–50.
- Oyinloye, J., & Adekola, M. (2023). Moodle's role in enhancing blended learning within teacher education programs in Nigeria. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Sciences*, 63, 69–79. *Journal of Educational Technology and Innovation*, 12(3), 45–62. <https://doi.org/10.61414/jeti.v5i4>
- Petrovaite, E. (2023). Mall-based LMS: A comparative study of Canvas and Moodle. Retrieved from <https://e-spacio.uned.es/entities/publication/3a15935d-5e91-4a41-93c8-25373aef4d85/full>
- Pujasari, R. S., & Ruslan, R. (2021). Utilizing Canvas in technology enhanced language learning classroom: A case study. *The Journal of English Literacy Education: The Teaching and Learning of English as a Foreign Language*, 8(1), 42-54.
- Reid, A. (2019). Climate change education and research: possibilities and potentials versus problems and perils? *Environmental Education Research*, 25(6), 767-790.
- Salah, S., & Thabet, M. (2021). E-learning management systems: A feature-based comparative analysis. *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, 18, e202118003. DOI: 10.4301/S1807-1775202118003

- Singh, R., Kumar, S., & Reddy, P. (2023). Effect of gamification tools in Moodle on student engagement: An experimental study *Journal of Educational Technology*, 18(1), 45–60. <https://www.googleadservices.com>
- Srivastava, S. (2023). Impact of blended learning models on secondary education student engagement and academic performance *International Journal of Novel Research and Development (IJNRD)*.
- Tselios, N., Filippidi, A., & Komis, V. (2010). Impact of Moodle usage practices on students' performance in blended learning. *Academia*.
- UNESCO. (2017). *Annual report for 2017*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Available from: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/>
- Williams, A., & Zhao, L. (2022). Canvas and Moodle in hybrid STEM courses: A comparative study *Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 102–118.
- Zhang, Y., Ghandour, A., & Shestak, V. (2020). Using learning analytics to predict student performance in Moodle LMS *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 15(20), 102–113. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i20.15915>
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2020). *Self-regulated learning theory and academic achievement*. [Unpublished manuscript]